

Social Innovation for Poverty Reduction in the Special Region of Yogyakarta

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Abstract:- The problem of poverty is one of the fundamental problems that are the centre of government attention. One crucial aspect of supporting poverty reduction strategies is the availability of accurate and targeted poverty data. The availability of accurate poverty data is a must for a successful poverty reduction program. The problem is that the poverty data available in Indonesia is quite diverse. This study wants to examine the efforts to reduce poverty in Sleman Regency through innovations that have been carried out. The approach used is descriptive qualitative. The results showed that the breakthrough made by the Sleman local government has carried out social innovation with the Lasamba program through the stages of initiation, development and implementation of determining recipients of poverty programs. In addition, the Sleman Regency policy is to form a Poverty Alleviation Team starting from padukuhan or hamlets to the sub-district level, which involves elements of the government, non-governmental organizations, and the business world. These efforts have shown results with a reduction in poverty rates and the accuracy of beneficiaries of poverty alleviation programs in the Sleman Regency.

Keywords:- *Povert; Social Innovation; poverty alleviation team.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The poverty problem is one of the fundamental problems that are the centre of government attention. A critical aspect of supporting the Poverty Reduction Strategy is the availability of accurate and targeted poverty data. Poverty data based on the Social Protection Program Data Collection (PPLS/ *Pendataan Program Perlindungan Sosial*) cannot be separated from the influence of the poverty line and the different ways of looking at poverty in each region in Indonesia. Poverty criteria and different perspectives will lead to different interpretations of the number of poor people, the criteria for the poor and the level of handling of the poverty problem.^[1]

The analyzed poverty data will also be used to evaluate government policies on poverty issues, compare poverty across time and regions, and determine the target of the poor to improve their condition through a poverty alleviation program. In order to implement various poverty reduction programs, information about who is poor and where they are very important and will become the essential data in targeting poverty alleviation. For poverty reduction programs to be successful and on target, the availability of reliable poverty data is a necessity. The Minister of Home

Affairs Regulation Number 42 of 2010 concerning Provincial and Regency/City Poverty Reduction Coordination Teams, it is stated in article 1 that poverty reduction programs are activities carried out by the government, regional governments, businesses, and the community to improve the welfare of the poor through social assistance and assistance empowerment.^[2]

The development of poverty alleviation will not be effective if it is not synergized with existing supporting programs in the regions. The economic, social, cultural, legal, and security fields significantly influence poverty alleviation in the area. Things that need to be considered by regions that have problems regarding poverty alleviation include the Special Region of Yogyakarta known as DIY. Poverty and income inequality are still homework for the DIY. Until now, the poverty rate in the DIY has reached 13.1% or the highest in Java.^[1]

The poverty rate percentage is the highest in Java and the third lowest nationally. This poverty rate also needs our attention and scrutiny regarding the poverty line standard referred to by the Central Statistics Agency (BPS/*Badan Pusat Statistik*), which only uses an income standard of IDR 360,169 per person per capita per month. With the deficient standard of BPS, namely an income of IDR 360.000 per month, the figure is 13.1%. In fact, the actual figure in the field might be bigger. Besides having the highest poverty rate in Java, the DIY also has nationally the highest income inequality rate. The gap between rich and poor in the DIY is the highest, at 0.43 compared to the national ratio of 0.3. The DIY Income Inequality Index shows that the income of the highest 20% of the population is more than three times the lowest 40% of the population. According to the World Bank, one of the essential records of success in reducing poverty is changing the role of the government in tackling poverty. Good governance is the main recipe for the success of poverty reduction efforts.^[3]

Efforts to tackle poverty in the DIY have been carried out, including by Sleman Regency. The Sleman Regency Government has made the first innovation breakthrough in an integrated referral service system. This system helps identify the needs of the poor and vulnerable and connects them with programs and services managed by the central, provincial, and district/city governments according to their needs. This system also helps identify complaints of the poor and vulnerable, make referrals, and assist in handling complaints to ensure that these complaints are handled correctly.

The second innovation is to create a one-stop service regarding poverty data, often referred to as an independent updating mechanism used as the basis or object of the target who will benefit from the poverty alleviation program. Independent data updating is carried out from the village level regarding poverty data analyzed based on the PPFM integrated database, which contains specifications, standards, and verification processes. This verification directly checks the object's condition of the object program target to be carried out.

The third innovation in poverty alleviation carried out in the Sleman Regency is forming a regional poverty reduction coordination team. This organization was formed to streamline poverty alleviation in the Sleman district because the poverty alleviation team was formed from the district, sub-district, village, and *padukuhan* or hamlets levels. This poverty alleviation team is flexible and can be filled by people who have expertise in poverty management involving local governments, community leaders, and the private sector.

The four innovation is by utilizing Corporate Social Responsibility funds from companies in the Sleman Regency can be utilized by beneficiary families from *Program Keluarga Harapan* (PKH) - which translated to the Family Hope Program - to form a collaborative socio-economic group adapted to the existing regional potential. The government has implemented poverty reduction programs since the enactment of Presidential Regulation number 15 of 2010 concerning the Acceleration of Poverty Reduction. In the new government, Presidential Regulation Number 166 of 2014 was issued concerning the Acceleration of Poverty Reduction Program. Poverty alleviation is carried out by policies by the central and regional governments that are carried out systematically, planned and in synergy between the business world and the community to reduce the number of poor people to improve the degree of community welfare. With the implementation of Presidential Regulation Number 166 of 2014, the government launched the Integrated Database Update. It is a national activity aimed at ensuring the Integrated Database as the main component in the targeting system for poverty reduction programs in Indonesia. This integrated database displays information on socio-economic conditions.

This poverty data collection becomes a reference for formulating policies to reduce poverty and remembering the urgency of providing poverty data in the regions. The TKPKD or Regional Poverty Reduction Coordination Team is a follow-up to the program.

Things that have been done in the regional government's social protection efforts are a step to overcome poverty in promoting community welfare. The flagship program claimed by the government, one of which is in the Sleman district, is *Program Keluarga Harapan* (PKH). Data on health facilities in Sleman Regency in 2018, PKH recipients experienced an increase from an average of 56,909 KPM from 65,501 KPM who visited health facilities.^[4]

For the Development of Nutritional Status in Sleman Regency from 2013 to 2018, the data shows that good nutritional status tends to fluctuate up and down with a range between 88.86% to 90.30% during the last five years. Meanwhile, the status of poor nutrition and undernourishment tends to decrease. The percentage of nutritional status is more volatile and has increased in the last 3 years. The implementation of nutritional surveillance activities in 2018 includes Monitoring of Nutritional Status with BB/U, TB/U, and BB/TB standards.

The potential for regional development in Sleman Regency is very open. Because when viewed from all regencies in the DIY, Sleman Regency is a district with the highest regional income and has access to human resources and many public and private universities that can be used as an initiator of the development of innovation in poverty alleviation. The local government of Sleman Regency can collaborate between universities, the private sector, and the government to develop new ideas for poverty alleviation. If these three elements can be carried out, they will be able to create an innovation that can be the basis for formulating policies regarding poverty.

The role of the government in poverty alleviation is explained. First, the Regional Government is a facilitator, creating conducive conditions for implementing development. Second, the Regional Government is a regulator, preparing directions and policies. Third, the Regional Government is a dynamist, mobilizing the participation of all elements in the community. Fourth, the Regional Government is the coordinator, integrating poverty reduction-based programs through participatory planning mechanisms.

Poverty alleviation in the regions can take advantage of the role of the industrial sector in supporting national economic growth. The industrialization strategy plays a vital role in being the main driver of economic growth and the development of expanding job opportunities, fulfilling people's basic needs, increasing and distributing people's income, and alleviating people from poverty. UU no. 40 of 2007 concerning Limited Liability Companies Article 74 states that companies must carry out Corporate Social Responsibility from the company's profits.^[5]

The poverty problem with its various characteristics is not easy to solve without the involvement of all elements. The primary key to poverty reduction efforts in the regions is the establishment and institutionalization of communication, coordination and cooperation networks from the three pillars that exist in the regions: local governments, communities and care groups, Non-Governmental Organizations, private sector, universities, *ulama*/community leaders. The poverty problem can only be overcome if the three components above work together in the spirit of togetherness and participate in finding alternative poverty criteria, poverty data collection, targeting, problem-solving, and poverty reduction efforts to be more objective and on target.

The facts on the ground show that the poverty reduction policies carried out so far still have many weaknesses in poverty reduction policies. Government policies based on experience in poverty alleviation have several weaknesses. They are (1) still oriented towards macro growth without paying attention to the aspect of equity, (2) policies that are centralized, (3) more caricative than transformative, (4) positioning society as an object rather than a subject, (5) an orientation towards poverty alleviation that tends to be creative and momentary rather than sustainable productivity, and (6) a generic perspective and solution to the existing poverty problem without paying attention to the existing plurality (Multifiah, 2011). Due to the varied nature of the challenges, the handling of the poverty problem must touch the actual source and root of the problem, either directly or indirectly.

In understanding poverty in the Sleman Regency, it is essential to pay attention to the locality in each region, namely poverty at the local level determined by the community and local government. The implementation of the poverty reduction program aims to improve the welfare of the poor from two sides. First, increasing income by increasing productivity so that the poor can manage, obtain opportunities, and protect to obtain better works in various economic, social, cultural, and political activities. Second, poverty reduction reduces the burden of basic needs such as access to education, health, and infrastructure that facilitates and supports socio-economic activities. For this reason, strategic steps are needed to accelerate poverty reduction and build partnerships between various sectors in the Sleman Regency.

II. METHODS

This research used a qualitative approach in the form of a case study which is a research strategy that requires researchers to carefully investigate a program, event, activity, process, or group of individuals.^[6] The method used was the case study method as presented.^[7] Case studies were used as a comprehensive explanation relating to various aspects of a person, a group, an organization, a program, or a social situation being researched, sought and studied as profoundly as possible. This research was conducted in the Sleman Regency, The Special Region of Yogyakarta. This regency is bordered by Central Java Province in the north and east, Gunung Kidul Regency, Bantul Regency and Yogyakarta City in the south, and Kulon Progo Regency in the west.

Data collection techniques were carried out using observation, interviews and documentation studies. Observations are carried out by systematically observing and recording the symptoms that appear on the object of observation research, divided into two, namely direct and indirect observations. Meanwhile, interviews in this study were conducted when collecting information that was not obtained from observation. The key informants in this research interview were the regent and deputy regent, regional secretary, head of social services, head of the Regional Planning Agency, head of BPS Sleman and members of the Regional People's Representative Council. After the observations and interviews were carried out, the next step was to study documentation which is a technique of collecting data and analyzing documents, whether written, illustrated, or electronically.^[8]

Data analysis was carried out after primary and secondary data had been collected. The next step was preparing and organizing the data (text data such as transcripts or image data such as photographs) for analysis, then reducing the data into themes through the process of coding and summarizing the code and finally presenting the data in the form of a chart, table or discussion. Qualitative data analysis techniques are data reduction, data presentation and conclusion drawing. This process continues throughout the research, even before the data is collected.^[9]

III. RESULT

Tahun	Number of Poor population (000)	Percentage of Poor Population
2016	96,63	8,21
2017	96,75	8,13
2018	92,04	7,65
2019	90,17	7,41
2020	99,78	8,12

Table 1: Number and Percentage of Poor Population in Sleman Regency March 2016 - March 2020

Source: Susenas March 2016 – March 2020

Table 1 shows the number of poor population in the Sleman Regency from March 2016 to March 2020. Poverty conditions in this Regency during this period were quite volatile, but in the last year, there was a significant increase. From the results of the *Susenas* in March 2020, the poor population in the Sleman Regency is 99.78 thousand people. Compared with the results of the *Susenas* in March 2019, where the number of poor people at that time was 90.17 thousand people, this condition showed an increase in the

number of poor people in this Regency by 9.61 thousand people or an increase of 10.65 percent.

The percentage of the poor population in the Sleman Regency in 2020 has increased after experiencing a decline in recent years. In March 2020, the percentage of the poor was recorded at 8.12 percent, an increase of 0.71 percentage points compared to the condition in the previous year, which was recorded at 7.41 percent (March 2019).

Fig. 2: Number of Poor Population in Sleman Regency March 2016 - March 2020 (in thousands of people)

Source: *Susenas* March 2016 - March 2020

During the period March 2016 - March 2019, the poverty situation in this Regency tends to improve (Figure 2). In March 2016, the poor population was recorded at 96.63 thousand people. This number continued to experience a downward trend until 2019, although it rose slightly in 2017. In March 2020, the poor population

experienced a reasonably high increase to 99.78 thousand people.

In the last five years, the poverty rate in the Sleman Regency has fluctuated with a downward trend until 2019 and increased in 2020, as is shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3: Percentage of Poor Population in the Sleman Regency March 2016 – March 2020

Source: *Susenas* March 2016 - March 2020

From March 2016 to March 2019, the percentage of the poor population in the Sleman Regency decreased from 8.21 percent to 7.41 percent. During this period, the poverty percentage continued to decline. In March 2020, the percentage of the poor population rose to 8.12 percent.

IV. DISCUSSION

A. Social Innovation for Poverty Reduction in the Special Region of Yogyakarta

The Social Innovation process for poverty alleviation in the Sleman Regency is divided into 3 stages, namely the initiation stage, the development stage and the implementation stage.

Social innovation aims to solve the problems that the community faces so that what is meant by better is the condition of the community, which is the beneficiaries'

target. After the 1998 economic crisis, the Indonesian government began designing and implementing various programs specifically aimed at the poor. The government at that time launched *Program Jaringan Pengaman Sosial* (JPS)– which translated to the Social Safety Net Program, which aimed to protect the fields of food, health, education, and access to sources of income for people who were already poor before the economic crisis, and people who became poor due to the impact of the economic crisis. Among the various JPS programs, the highest target number of participants/beneficiaries are the rice subsidy program for poor households (originally called Special Market Operations or OPK, later became the *Raskin* Program) and Health Assistance known as JPS-BK. The target participants/beneficiaries of these programs are Pre-Prosperous and Prosperous Families-1 based on the National Family Planning Coordinating Board or BKKBN. The Regional Empowerment Program in Overcoming the Impact

of the Economic Crisis (PDMDKE) is a program of assistance from the government in revolving credit funds intended for the poor and unemployed due to the 1997-1998 economic crisis. The target groups in this program are households belonging to the Pre-Prosperous Family, Prosperous Family 1, and the unemployed. Assistance funds are given to almost every village in Indonesia. With the amount of the funds adjusted to the size of the village concerned. The aid funds can be used for physical development activities and productive economic activities.

Several social protection programs in the 2000s era were quite popular, including the School Operational Assistance program], known as BOS, in the Education sector, which assisted in operational funds for schools in Indonesia. In the health sector, there is a health insurance program called Health Insurance for the Poor –known as *askeskin*, which later transformed into the Community Health Insurance Program, known as *jamkesmas*, then became Contribution Assistance Recipients (PBI) of the National Health Insurance System (JKN). There is the Subsidized Rice program for Low-Income Communities in the food sector, which results from a change from the previous program, Special Market Operations or OPK. The government also provided direct assistance in the form of cash as compensation for the poor for the increase in the price of fuel oil in 2005 and 2009. This program was known as the Direct Cash Assistance program or BLT program, which later changed to Community Temporary Assistance (BLSM) when the fuel price hike happened again in 2013.

In 2005, through BPS, the government conducted Socio-Economic Data Collection (PSE 2005). The main objective of PSE 2005 is to identify target households receiving BLT Program as compensation for the reduction in fuel subsidies. However, in addition to the BLT program, PSE 2005 data was also used for targeting *askeskin* program, which was later known as the Community Health Insurance or *jamkesmas* and the *Raskin* Program.

In 2008, to distribute the BLT Program, BPS as the person in charge of providing data on the target households receiving BLT, conducted a household socio-economic data collection known as the Social Protection Program Data Collection (PPLS, 2008). The primary data for PPLS 2008 is PSE 2005 data which was updated with verification results in 1,023 sub-districts in 97 regencies/cities in 15 provinces in the pilot area of the Family Hope Program; that is, the final result was 19,018,057 targeted households. The ranking of household welfare status based on the 2008 PPLS still uses the RTSM, RTM, and RTHM classifications. Unlike the PSE 2005, the PPLS 2008 uses 14 household variables in the PSE 2005 plus 8 individual variables (household members), and the Proxy Means Testing model to determine the ranking of the household welfare status being recorded.

In 2010, the National Team for the Acceleration of Poverty Reduction (TNP2K) was established as a forum for cross-sectoral and cross-stakeholder coordination at the national level to accelerate poverty reduction. Through TNP2K, the government has begun implementing more

structured poverty reduction programs. The poverty reduction program is divided into four clusters. Cluster 1 is a group of aid and social protection-based poverty reduction programs to fulfil fundamental rights, reduce the burden of life, and improve the quality of life of the poor. Then, cluster 2 is a group of community empowerment-based poverty reduction programs. After that, cluster 3 is a group of poverty reduction programs based on the empowerment of micro and small economic enterprises. The last, cluster 4 is a group of pro-people programs.

In 2011, BPS conducted PPLS (PPLS, 2011) again by taking advantage of the momentum of the 2010 Population Census, which is an update of Indonesia's population data as a whole. The main objective of PPLS 2011 is to develop an Integrated Database for social protection programs.

Although various efforts have been made to reduce poverty and vulnerability, the number of poor and vulnerable people remains high. The Central Statistics Agency recorded that the number of poor people in March 2017 was 27.77 million people or approximately 10.64%. In addition, people above the poverty line are vulnerable to falling into poverty if they face an economic shock or crisis. The income distribution gap is also widening, and the increase can see in Indonesia's Gini ratio from 0.35 in 2009 to 0.393 in March 2017. Likewise, the gap between rural and urban areas is still high. In March 2017, poor people in rural areas were 13.93%, higher than 7.72% in urban areas. Many poor and vulnerable families do not receive comprehensive social protection services despite being eligible for assistance.

Services and handling of social problems that have not been optimal stems from the lack of integration in the implementation of social services. Many sectoral service programs are still running, following each institution's main tasks and functions independently. Law Number 11 of 2009 has mandated that the implementation of social welfare carried out by the central and regional governments and the community must be directed, sustainable, and integrated.

In the Sleman Regency, ways to overcome poverty are developed in various, more comprehensive ways. In 2008, the first generation poverty information system was developed based on the regulation of the Sleman regent number 21 to map low-income families in receiving poverty programs with fourteen poverty indicators. After implementing the poverty information system and developing it better in terms of scope and usability, in 2009, a second-generation poverty information system was formed until 2012; this second-generation poverty system can survive after experiencing two generations of poverty in the Sleman district. The local government has a shared passion for building a complete data system. Every relevant agency with a poverty alleviation program can provide programs to beneficiary families to be right on target.

After experiencing changes in the poverty system of the first and second generations, the Sleman local government is trying to combine regional poverty data with poverty data that the centre has carried out through data

collection on social protection programs, better known as PPLS 2011. After receiving PPLS 2011 data from the central government, the regional poverty system was redeveloped in 2013. Services and handling of social problems which has not been optimal stems from the lack of integration in the implementation of social services. Many sectoral service programs are still running, following each institution's main tasks and functions independently. Law Number 11 of 2009 has mandated that the implementation of social welfare carried out by the central and regional governments and the community must be directed, sustainable, and integrated.

Local governments have a mandate to provide essential services to improve people's welfare. Local governments also have sufficient resources to implement social protection and poverty reduction programs, both from central transfers and local revenue. However, the authority and magnitude of these resources are not matched by adequate capacity in managing social protection programs and poverty alleviation and are currently better known as SLRT. SLRT is a service system that helps identify the needs of the poor and vulnerable poor and connects them with social protection programs² and poverty reduction³ organized by the government, both central, provincial, and district/city governments according to their needs. The SLRT also helps identify complaints from the poor and vulnerable to the poor, make referrals, and monitor complaints to ensure that these complaints are handled correctly. The objective of SLRT is to increase the effectiveness and efficiency of social protection systems to reduce poverty, vulnerability and inequality.

In connection with this, the concept of implementing the Integrated Service and Referral System in Sleman Regency is to place the Sembada SLRT secretariat at the Sleman Regency Social Service as the gateway for social services and complaints at the Social Service. Following the needs of residents who come to complain and ask for social services that continue to develop and require appropriate and fast solutions, the Sleman District Social Service also prepares support, both from regulatory support, budget and human resources that can meet the needs of the community. In the national priority for poverty reduction in 2018, the government focuses on accelerating poverty reduction and equitable growth for the lowest 40% of the population. This effort is carried out by implementing targeted social security and assistance programs, meeting basic needs, and expanding access to micro, small and cooperative enterprises.

The following human resources support the implementation of the Sembada SLRT in the Sleman Regency. The SLRT managers are 3 people from Social Service, Development Planning Agency (Bappeda), and Regional Research and Development, Communication and Information Office (Diskominfo), 11 back office officers (all structural officials of Social Service become SLRT back office officers), 8 front office officers, 3 *Ngantar Paimah* officers, 25 *Lasamba* officers, 17 SLRT supervisors (1 subdistrict one supervisor) and 86 SLRT facilitators in 86 villages throughout the Sleman Regency.

The management of the Sembada SLRT at the Social Service Office of the Sleman Regency since the beginning of its growth in late 2016 has been strongly supported by relevant agencies, such as Bappeda, Diskominfo, Health Office and other agencies. Regarding budget support, the implementation of the SLRT in the Sleman Regency is strongly supported by the Sleman Regency budget team. One of the SLRT managers comes from Bappeda, so information on the implementation and benefits of SLRT can already be known directly by themselves as the activity and budget planner. During the Covid-19 pandemic, the SLRT budget also experienced a budget reallocation, but it did not affect the services and referrals provided by the SLRT Sembada Social Service of Sleman Regency.

Handling social problems is very complex and requires innovative ways to handle them quickly and precisely. In Sleman Regency, the handling of social problems is carried out with an approach adapted to the regional motto called SEMBADA, which stands for Smile, Empathy, Serving, Sharing, Dedicated, Trustworthy, Disciplined and Accountable. Problems often encountered in the Sleman Regency include health and education, all of which lead to poverty. With the problems faced, innovations are needed that can support solving these problems. To make it happen, the Sleman district carried out an innovation program called LASAMBA (sambaing citizen service).

The Lasamba program is from the Sleman Regency Social Service, which was officially launched on 27-08-2018 in padukuhan Sembung, Sukoharjo Ngaglik Sleman. It is an innovation from the Social Service of Sleman Regency that used a ball pick-up system. It means that the government will go directly to visit residents to realize the quality of improving the quality of the public, especially for underprivileged residents who need social services and social assistance without having to apply first to the Department of Social Affairs. To support this program, in providing public services to the community, this program is supported by the quick reaction team and 25 personnel from District Social Welfare staff (TKSK), Community Social Workers (PSM) and PKH Facilitator so the program can be faster and more complete. The Lasamba program has changed the service system from one direction to two. This program is an essential part of the bureaucratic culture to be more responsive to the community's needs, so it does not wait but picks up and solves residents' problems. Currently, there are approximately 77 residents served by the Lasamba program.^[10]

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and analysis, it can be concluded that alleviating poverty in the Sleman area has resulted in innovation in the form of citizen sambaing services or the Lasamba program. This method used a regional approach to reach people who need social assistance. The Regional Government of Sleman Regency has formed a poverty alleviation team to the village level and has a complaint service regarding the poverty program.

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